

Towards energy-aware video streaming in 5G/B5G - application perspective

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Abstract—This paper presents an evaluation study on how the characteristics and amount of video traffic affect the energy consumption in different video applications utilising GPU and CPU processing, and in selected components of the 5G mobile network. The focus is put on the widely used HTTP adaptive streaming, which allows a flexible way for delivering dynamic content over the Internet for a variety of mobile devices with unique characteristics. However, these devices tend to maximise the processing performance with the highest available video quality, which leads to the penalty of higher energy consumption. In this paper, we show how different video quality affects the energy consumption in different parts of the components over 5G RAN, and evaluate selected video applications on energy usage basis. For this purpose, we use an accurate and system wide mobile test network for the evaluation with advanced energy measurement infrastructure. The extensive set of results with different video player applications verify that the use of smaller bitrates with decent QoS and QoE levels can reduce end-to-end energy consumption towards green networking.

Index Terms—Video streaming, applications, 5G, B5G, energy consumption

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile video traffic is expected to continue its growth especially in social media streaming services and can account up to 95% of total traffic on mobile networks [1]. As large number of users are using live social media streaming services both for producing as well as consuming content, it can form a huge impact for carbon footprint [2] especially in mobile networks relying on battery-powered user equipment (UE). With these aspects taken into account, we evaluate some of the most used open-source video player applications in terms of their energy consumption, and provide in-depth analysis and recommendations for their usage in adaptive video streaming.

In this work we focus on the video consumption perspective, which is considered as downlink (DL) traffic from the network point of view. That is, where the video content is consumed via depacketisation, decoding, and playback, possibly with multiple UEs requiring individual processing in each device resulting to higher total energy consumption. On the contrary, video encoding and packetisation for the production stream is typically done once, making its energy consumption less significant. However, the stream and codec parametrisation can partly dictate the bits to be processed with the tools developed according to the standardisation. For this purpose, we rely on H.264 standard which is still widely used in different streaming applications although usage of state-of-the encoders such

as high efficiency video coding (HEVC) and versatile video coding (VVC) can compress the data with higher compression efficiency [3], but higher power consumption [4].

As the majority of the content is available online accessed via wireless networks, the streaming protocols play an important role in delivering high quality videos either as video-on-demand (VoD) or live to users. Many of these protocols today favour for HTTP adaptive streaming (HAS) technologies enabling high flexibility against network fluctuations and therefore ensuring continuous playback even at mobile vehicle environment with high velocities. As fifth generation (5G) and beyond (B5G) cellular technology allow higher network speeds with improved processor technology, larger amount of data can be processed in UEs in real-time, which can lead to higher energy consumption and reduced battery life.

Literature and studies from the recent years regarding energy-savvy video streaming indicate its importance towards sustainability and green networking [5]. Many of the studies have been conducted in 4G/LTE networks using mobile devices [6] and also using HAS streaming protocols [7]. However, the recent studies tend to lack in-depth component evaluation in real measurement environment. By taking these challenges into account, this paper contributes with the following novel aspects:

- Provide in-depth and accurate measurements using real video streaming setup, 5G network, and energy measurement infrastructure,
- Identify how the adaptive HTTP streaming with the recent high- and ultra-high definitions affect on energy consumption in different physical components during mobile streaming,
- Identify how video parametrisation and use of GPU affect on player's energy consumption,
- Provide future recommendations for high quality, energy-aware mobile streaming.

This paper is organised as follows. Section II introduces the HAS protocol and energy-savvy practices from the literature in order to save energy for mobile video in UEs and radio access network (RAN). In Section III, we depict our real test network environment, the evaluation setup, and used applications with their specific parameters and configurations for the selected test cases. Section IV illustrates our results and analyses the results, and finally Section V, draws the conclusion.

II. MOBILE VIDEO STREAMING IN 5G/B5G FOR REDUCED ENERGY

A. Characteristics of 5G/B5G for mobile video

The standardisation for 6G [8] has already started to emphasize the importance of reduced energy consumption especially in base stations (BS) with the use of renewable energy [9]. As the 5G favours for denser placement of cells due to higher carrier frequencies, total energy consumption of a 5G site forms a significant factor in the total end-to-end (E2E) transmission chain from the origin server to client UEs. The features of 5G and B5G for mobile video are transformative, allowing improved experiences. These technologies seek to improve data rates of up to 10 Gbps, which is essential for streaming 4K and 8K ultra high-definition videos for a large number of users, and above 10 Gbps to guarantee smoother and instantaneous streaming for immersive video experiences [10], such as extended reality (XR). The authors [11] provide an experimental methodology and measurements of low-latency video streaming over a commercial 5G network, under both static and mobility scenarios. 5G/B5G is also poised to make it possible to use even more sophisticated formats, such as volumetric and holographic videos, remote surgery, etc. which call for extremely high bandwidth and low latency. 5G enhances energy efficiency, enabling devices that stream video to have longer battery lives and B5G will aim for even better energy efficiency, particularly as new technologies like AI-driven encoding/decoding emerge and video content grows increasingly data-intensive. In the 5G era, AI is already incorporated for video compression and network performance optimization. As AI becomes more prevalent, more sophisticated video streaming services will emerge that are able to anticipate user behavior, precaching content, and maximize network capacity for continuous streaming.

5G incorporates the integration of multiaccess edge computing (MEC), enabling real-time interactive video applications and lowering latency by bringing content delivery and video processing closer to the user. In order to improve real-time video analytics, personalized content distribution, and intelligent caching for smooth video experiences, B5G will further incorporate artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning at the edge [12]. In terms of improved quality of experience (QoE), 5G minimizes buffering and interruptions by ensuring that customers receive the best video quality available based on network circumstances with adaptive bit rate streaming and edge computing. Adaptive streaming will be further improved by B5G, enabling compatibility for more sophisticated media formats including volumetric video (3D capture and playback) and 16K video. So we see that 5G significantly boosts capacity and data rates, and reduces latency, which improves the dependability and quality of mobile video streaming. Using technologies such as AI, edge computing, and ultra-HD video formats to achieve even more immersive experiences, B5G expands existing developments and sets new standards for mobile video applications in the future.

B. HTTP adaptive streaming

Today's mobile networks are expected to work reliably with high quality of service (QoS) at any time and place for the users enjoying the social media and streaming services characterized with varying length of video clips. The majority of such services are based on HAS [13], which allows high dynamic flexibility against network fluctuations. As today, Apple HTTP Live Streaming (HLS), dynamic adaptive streaming over HTTP (MPEG-DASH or DASH), Microsoft Smooth Streaming (MSS), and Adobe HTTP dynamic streaming (HDS) are the dominants for HAS streaming.

In HAS, the stream is divided into representations, each consisting of smaller, usually 1-10 second video segments. The representations can vary by the most common parameters, such as bitrate, resolution, or frame rate enabling a tolerance against network fluctuations. A playlist file at the beginning of the streaming session depicts the stream structure and available representations to the clients. With the context of DASH in this work, the media description protocol (.mpd) file is used.

Due to the wide deployment of DASH, it holds the H.264 support for variety of video applications and resolutions up to 8K. However, novel codecs such as AV1, H.265, and ultimately H.266 all lead to improved compression efficiency, which are required for future greener networking where the amount of bits can influence on E2E energy consumption. In this work we focus on H.264, one of the still widely used codec in order to gain baseline for future explorations especially from energy consumption perspective.

From energy consumption perspective, DASH provides interesting point with its buffered transmission of the video segments. By this, the client application can define how much data is buffered before the actual decoding and playback for guaranteeing smooth QoE. In this paper, we use minimal video buffering to first have a holistic view of the energy consumption in different components in the E2E architecture.

C. Energy-Efficient RAN

Mobile networks consumed 650 GWh energy during 2022 in Finland alone [14]. According to GSMA Energy Efficiency Benchmarking project, on the average 76% of energy consumed by mobile operators is consumed in radio access networks (RAN) and its supplementary functions, such as cooling [15]. These numbers indicate the importance of minimizing the RAN energy consumption while still keeping the required QoS for the services it is running.

There are several factors affecting the energy consumption of a 5G base station site. Most of these factors are static such as the number of carriers and cells, which define how many radio units are installed, the number of transmitters per radio unit, available bandwidth per carrier, and the maximum downlink (DL) power per cell [16], [17]. These static factors are typically selected in radio network planning such that the QoS requirements of the busy hour traffic can be fulfilled. The main dynamic factor for the energy consumption is the level of physical resource block (PRB) usage, which depends on the traffic load.

Traffic in mobile networks is typically bursty in nature and varies significantly in time [18]. For example, the cells providing capacity for areas with mostly office buildings have very little traffic during the early morning hours. Thus, the biggest energy saving potential is achieved by dynamically switching off cells and carriers (cell sleep modes) with only little traffic demand. When the cell has to be available due to coverage reasons, additional energy savings can be effectively achieved by temporarily switching off transmitters and by enabling discontinuous transmission (DTX) [19]. When DTX is enabled and there is no data to be transmitted from the base station, power amplifiers and other RF components can be switched off lowering the idle power consumption. This emphasizes the importance of DTX-aware scheduling. If the served traffic load is low and it can tolerate small delays, it is a good strategy to buffer DL data such that base station can enter DTX for longer periods of time [20].

III. EVALUATION ENVIRONMENT

A. 5G/B5G Test network

The empirical measurements for this study were done using our private 5G standalone (SA) network in Oulu, Finland. The network is completely self-operated, which allows tailoring the network configuration and functionalities for the targeted scenario. Our frequency licenses allow operation on several FR1 frequency division duplex (FDD) and time division duplex (TDD) bands as well as at n258 FR2 band. The outdoor TDD coverage is implemented by massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) radio units, which enable testing various beamforming scenarios. 5G base stations are equipped with commercial operator-grade base station hardware that enable realistic energy consumption measurements. The measurements in this study were done in one of our outdoor cells. The set of base station parameters relevant for interpreting the results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
RELEVANT BASE STATION PARAMETERS

Radio type	massive-MIMO, 64 transmitters
Cell type	n78 TDD, 30 kHz subcarrier spacing
Bandwidth	60 MHz
Time slot division	DL:UL 4:1
Max. DL Tx power	200 W
Max. DL rank	4
DTX	enabled
Discontinuous reception (DRX)	enabled, long cycle 160 ms, inactivity timer 80 ms, on-duration timer 10 ms

B. Energy and network measurement framework

Accurate energy measurement is integrated as a part of the 5G/B5G test network comprising various indoor and outdoor small cells radio units, system modules, baseband units, edge servers, and UEs. The energy measurement system for aforementioned high power components uses Carlo Gavazzi

Fig. 1. The simplified evaluation setup with measurement points.

automation tools [21] (0.1 watt accuracy) and Otii Ace Pro [22] for low-power reliable UE measurements (mW accuracy) without intervention or influence to the performance of system components. The high power components are integrated with single- and three-phase measurement devices with the ability to read power values in real-time in one second intervals, and to be further pushed into database.

The network performance measurement system for the server and client devices utilises Qosium [23] and is integrated as a part of the test network infrastructure for providing reliable QoS statistics. Qosium Probes are installed into the specific components of the evaluated E2E measurement path depicted in Fig. 1. Qosium uses passive measurement technology without interfering the measured transmission signal. Qosium Scope is used for gathering the measurement information from the Probes, which further passes this data to Influx database for later analysis. In this work, we will report the sent and received throughputs between the origin server and client measured in one second intervals.

In addition to Qosium, in-built BS counters are used for investigating the cell and radio channel performance and capacity in detail. In this work, we also examine how efficiently channel resources are utilized for different video rates, beyond just basic channel information. However, cell-side statistics are gathered less frequently i.e. once per minute.

C. Video streaming setup and applications

The most essential gNB parameters of our 5G/B5G test network infrastructure during the experiments are illustrated in Table I with the video streaming setup according to Fig. 1. The origin video server, functioning as an edge server of the network with fixed network connection, is in charge of hosting the VoD service (Caddy web server). In the client side, we have one dedicated video client connected with fixed USB connection to the Sierra Wireless EM9293 5G NR modem with M.2 developer kit functioning as the mobile access point. Power consumption of the video server and clietn were measured using the Gavazzi devices devices directly from the power sockets, whereas mode was measured using more accurate Otii Ace Pro. The displays of the machines were not included as a part of the energy measurement.

For the evaluative tests, we pre-encoded four test streams using H.264 compression (level 5.1), fixed frame rate 30 fps, and DASH encapsulation with 1s segment lengths. The streams, however, were encoded with varying resolution and bitrate to

enable adaptivity: 720p@3 Mbit/s; 1080p@10 Mbit/s, 4K@40 Mbit/s, and 8K@100 Mbit/s, which all represent the current bitrate vs. resolution recommendations for AVC video coding used by the popular video service platforms, as well as 5G XR recommendations [24]. Thus, constant bitrate encoding was used to avoid high data traffic peaks and therefore causing also power consumption peaks in the measured devices.

Four different adaptive DASH supported video player applications were selected for Linux (Ubuntu 22.04) operating environment with Intel NUC mini-PC and AMD Radeon RX Vega M graphics card. The selection of these video players was based on earlier familiarity and ability to utilise both CPU and GPU processing during the decoding and playback. Thus, the purpose of this work was not solely to compare or find the most energy-aware software amongst the players, but to identify the parametrisation and GPU processing affect to energy consumption. We used minimal network & playback buffering commonly for all the tested players:

- GST-player - very basic media player provided by GStreamer open-source multimedia framework,
- VLC - commonly used open-source media player,
- MPV - open-source media player based on MPlayer and utilising FFmpeg decoding libraries,
- FFPlay - simple media player using FFmpeg libraries.

In addition to basic applications and playback functionalities, we configured and tested four different video output options with mpv:

1) *Null*: The `-vo=null` option disables any video output from the video player without additional computing overhead from drawing and presenting the video frames.

2) *OpenGL*: The `-vo=gpu -gpu-api=opengl` option uses OpenGL as a hardware accelerated rendering backend for drawing frames and presenting them onto an application window context. OpenGL is a mature graphics API used for offloading computer graphics and GPU compute operations onto a GPU using parallel computation architecture.

3) *Vulkan*: The `-vo=gpu -gpu=vulkan` option uses Vulkan as a hardware accelerated rendering backend for drawing and presenting frames onto a window context. Vulkan is a more recent graphics/compute API used for offloading calculations onto a GPU with minimal driver compared to OpenGL and allows more efficient use of the graphics driver. This allows developers to optimize programs further by minimizing the communication between CPU and GPU as well as by finely tuning the scheduling and submission of work.

4) *X11*: The `-vo=x11` option uses a CPU software renderer to draw and present frames onto an X11 window context. Some GPU usage may be possible on the behalf of the X11 window system for drawing application windows on the display, however the heavy lifting for drawing the video frames is done by the CPU. As most of the calculation are done on CPU, the performance of this renderer is typically much worse compared to options using hardware accelerated rendering.

As these options affect differently to GPU invocation it provides us more in-depth knowledge for energy consumption.

IV. RESULTS

In this Section, we highlight the findings of our measurements over 5G SA using the four different video streams with altering bitrate transmitted from the server to the video client using DASH streaming protocol. As a result from each of these 600-second long test runs, we gathered power consumption curves with one second intervals from each of the measured components, network throughputs both from server and UE, and CPU & GPU utilisation rates from the video client. During the tests, we limited other network usage and users to prevent interference, ensuring reliable results from a single test run for each evaluated player application and video stream. We translated the results into energy as a function of time according to

$$E = Pt \quad (1)$$

where E equals the consumed amount of energy with average power P and time t .

As the power and energy consists of the total device consumption, it is roughly the sum of video decoding, rendering (playback), CPU/GPU utilisation, and use of memory.

TABLE II
RELEVANT MEASURED STATISTICS FOR THE UE AND RADIO RESOURCES.

UE	RSRP (dB)	-79
	RSRQ (dB)	-11
	SINR (dB)	23
BS PHY	PRBs available per minute	15264000
	PRBs per slot	162
	PRBs used per minute	117943 (720p)
		267451 (1080p)
	928415 (4K)	
	2123662 (8K)	

A. Video UE

First we see the results from the video UE. Table II illustrates the signal values from the static UE and physical resource utilisation by the BS. The UE was located indoors with mobile connection to outdoor macro cell. From the signal strength (RSRP) perspective, the UE has a good coverage. Also the reported signal quality (RSRQ and SINR) indicates that the UE can be served with high QoS. Fig. 2 presents the data rates as an average between all the video applications measured from the video client with Qosium. As can be seen, the encoding rate control works very well for resolutions below 8K resulting to smooth bitrates.

Fig. 3 shows the total energy consumption of the video client with the different video applications conducted as separate runs. Hardware decoding (VA-API) was enabled for GST, VLC, and MPV-def while the others used purely SW decoding. From this figure we can observe several interesting factors. First, higher video resolution alongside with higher bitrate increases the energy consumption significantly especially when moving to 8K resolution regardless of the used application. Secondly, applications can be better optimized especially for HD and full HD resolutions. GST, VLC and MPV-default

Fig. 2. Received video throughput measured from the video client.

Fig. 3. Energy consumption for the evaluated playback applications against different video resolution.

are well optimised with the ability to use optimum share of CPU and GPU. However according to the debug logs, these aforementioned players were lacking HW decoding support for 8K falling back to SW decoding. Thirdly, we see that the other MPV video output options openGL, Vulkan, and X11 lead to increased energy consumption. In fact, the last two mentioned are unable decode and play the 8K stream in real time, which leads to high energy consumption and make their usage unacceptable.

Finally Fig. 4 illustrates the GPU and CPU usage for the selected applications. At this point MPV-vulkan and MPV-x11 were dropped out of investigation since they did not perform in real-time. From the results we see that there is no clear unambiguous relation between CPU/GPU usage and energy consumption. Clearly for MPV-null, which uses < 1% of GPU for all the video resolutions, leads also to lowest energy consumption for 8K. Interestingly GST can not utilise GPU for the highest resolution. In overall, VLC performs the best from all the applications since it can exploit both CPU and GPU in a coherent manner.

B. 5G network

In Table II the most relevant BS PRB allocation statistics are shown as averaged values of the test runs for each resolution. The 8K resolution with 100 Mbit/s stream consumes nearly 2123670 resource blocks per minute, which allocates nearly

Fig. 4. Average GPU and CPU usage for the video client.

14 % of the DL radio channel capacity according to PRBs availability. Thus, this means that the theoretical maximum for DL at the measurement location is around 800 Mbit/s with full allocation of the PRBs.

Fig. 5 presents the BS radio and 5G modem energy consumption against the video resolution. Similarly to the video client, higher bitrate aka resolution increases the radio and 5G modem power consumption. Energy consumption from the 5G modem perspective (Fig. 5) is very modest, approximately only 700 Joules for all the resolutions slightly increasing in line with video quality. This consumption increase is due to increasing data throughput, which increases both the amount of data for decoding at the 5G modem and the number of acknowledgments transmitted at uplink. As can be seen from Table II, DL PRB usage increases with the increasing video resolution. This directly results in increased DL Tx power per OFDM symbol and, consequently, in increased BS radio power consumption. The energy consumption at 5G modem slightly increases with the video resolution because of the increased number of bits to be decoded and also because of the increased number of UL acknowledgments for DL transport blocks. The BS baseband (BBU) power consumption stays quite constant, approx. 177 W resulting in 117 kJ energy per test run, for all resolutions.

Fig. 5. Average energy consumption for the 5G modem and BS radio against different video resolution.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we presented an empirical study with the aspect of energy consumption for video applications streaming VoD at different bitrates over 5G. We presented our research testbed and accurate measurement system harnessed to fully operate with the 5G/B5G test infrastructure. The gathered results from the essential components disclose the variety in energy consumption between the selected video player applications and especially when processing the higher resolutions 4K and 8K. The variation of energy consumption between the player applications is caused by different levels of SW code optimisation and use of CPU/GPU processing. Clearly, we see that high resolution combined with high bitrate causes significant energy consumption increase already for a single mobile client when considering the whole E2E transmission chain over 5G/B5G. Using smaller bitrates up to full HD resolution can still meet QoS and QoE requirements especially for smartphones, making it a simple option to reduce end-to-end energy consumption for greener networking.

As for future work the authors plan to extend the topic towards live streaming enhanced with mobility and go deeper on finding ways for reducing energy already during the encoding and in the BS/RAN via adaptive parametrisation depending on traffic volume and QoS requirements. Although the encoding is usually done once, setting proper video quality levels used by HTTP adaptive streaming are reflected also to energy consumption in the client, which creates need for dynamic intelligence and feedback signalling. In addition, the use of more advanced video codecs such as AV1 and H.265 can reduce the amount of needed bits which on the other hand reflect positively for RAN energy consumption. Intelligent and adaptive use of RAN parameters, such as sleep modes or proper DRX timing depending on the video traffic profile, can also lead to reduced 5G/B5G RAN energy consumption. Scalability with higher number of UEs is also essential future topic when considering the energy savings within the coverage of a base station.

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